

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Comparison of Audio Encoders for Audio-Text Contrastive Learning Representations

Sergio Cárdenas Gracia

Supervisor: Pablo Alonso Jiménez

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Abstract

This project investigates contrastive learning techniques for aligning audio and text representations in the music domain, focusing on scenarios with limited data and computational resources. We provide a comprehensive review of existing methods relevant to music-text contrastive learning. Two audio encoders, HTSAT and MAEST, initialized with pretrained weights, are integrated with a frozen RoBERTa text encoder within the LAION-AI CLAP framework and fine-tuned on the MTG-Jamendo dataset. Model performance is evaluated on three tasks: zero-shot genre classification on the GTZAN dataset, multi-label tag classification on the MagnaTagATune dataset, and text-to-music retrieval on the Song Describer dataset. Results show that HTSAT generalizes better in low-data settings, while MAEST tends to overfit, highlighting the impact of encoder complexity in resource-constrained environments. Attempts to mitigate MAEST's overfitting with weight decay and learning rate decay were unsuccessful. Additionally, the study highlights the critical role of data volume and batch size in contrastive learning effectiveness.

The source code for this work is publicly available at <https://github.com/SerX610/smc-master-thesis>.

Keywords: Audio-text representations; Contrastive learning; Encoders

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Multimodal representations enable the alignment of different types of data. In the case of music, audio and text data can be meaningfully related, such as audio signals paired with tags or text captions. One of the most common methods for achieving this alignment is contrastive learning, where audio and text are encoded and projected into a shared space. In this space, related audio-text pairs are positioned close together, while unrelated pairs are placed farther apart.

Contrastive learning has shown strong potential for modeling multimodal data, but research in text-audio multimodal representations for music remains relatively limited. Additionally, the availability of large, high-quality, open audio-text datasets for music is a challenge. Most existing datasets contain between 1,000 and 100,000 samples, significantly smaller than the massive datasets used to train current state-of-the-art contrastive models. In this context of limited data, the performance and potential of state-of-the-art audio encoders remain unexplored.

Therefore, this project provides an overview of the contrastive learning setting in the context of music, focusing on the evaluation and comparison of different audio encoders used to generate these multimodal representations.

1.2 Scope of the project

This project aims to provide a comprehensive review of existing contrastive learning approaches, particularly those applied to music and text. It includes a review of current methods and the identification of state-of-the-art audio and text encoders that are suitable for multimodal music representation.

By integrating these audio encoders into contrastive learning frameworks and fine-tuning them on small, publicly available datasets, the project evaluates their performance across several music-related tasks. The goal is to identify the most effective encoder configurations for producing robust and meaningful audio-text embeddings in the music domain.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This thesis begins with a detailed overview of state-of-the-art contrastive learning methods, highlighting the audio and text encoders they use and their training strategies.

Following this, the methodology employed during the project is described, including the training and evaluation procedures.

The results are then presented and discussed in the context of the project's objectives.

Finally, the thesis concludes with key findings, reflections, and suggestions for future work.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Contrastive learning

Contrastive learning is a machine learning technique where models learn by comparing pairs of data, bringing similar examples closer together in the representation space while pushing dissimilar ones further apart.

In the context of audio-text multimodal representations, two notable approaches with an open implementation have been proposed: Microsoft CLAP [1] and LAION-AI CLAP [2].

Microsoft CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining) is inspired by OpenAI's CLIP [3], which focuses on aligning text and image representations. Similarly, Microsoft CLAP uses an architecture composed of separate audio and text encoders, followed by linear projection layers that map both modalities into a shared embedding space.

LAION-AI CLAP builds on the Microsoft CLAP framework, using the same core architecture. However, it introduces a fusion mechanism designed to handle long audio clips. This mechanism works by downsampling the entire clip and randomly selecting three 10-second segments. These four audio representations (the downsample plus the three segments) are then combined into a single audio embedding.

While this fusion strategy shows promise for general audio, it performs poorly in the context of music. As a result, the fusion-based LAION-AI CLAP is not considered suitable for this project. Instead, the non-fusion variant of LAION-AI CLAP is chosen as the project’s baseline, as it offers a more recent and refined implementation compared to the original Microsoft CLAP.

2.2 Text encoders

Text encoders are essential for generating meaningful representations of textual data that can be matched with audio content. Current state-of-the-art text encoders for multimodal tasks are typically based on transformer architectures [4].

While OpenAI’s CLIP used a transformer-based text encoder trained from scratch, recent best practices in multimodal learning favor using pretrained language models such as BERT [5] or RoBERTa [6]. Microsoft CLAP adopts BERT as its text encoder, whereas LAION-AI CLAP uses RoBERTa.

Although other pretrained encoders have been explored in multimodal contexts, BERT and RoBERTa remain the most widely adopted for audio–text alignment, and the discussion here is therefore centered on them. Both produce high-quality, context-aware embeddings that can be aligned with audio representations. However, RoBERTa is considered a more optimized and robust variant of BERT, making it the preferred choice for current multimodal applications.

2.3 Audio encoders

Audio encoders are critical for extracting meaningful features from raw audio that can be aligned with textual descriptions.

In recent years, PANN [7] and HTSAT [8] have been widely selected as the primary audio encoders for multimodal tasks in the audio-text domain. PANN (Pre-trained Audio Neural Network) is a CNN-based audio classification model with 7 downsampling CNN blocks and 7 upsampling blocks. HTSAT (Hierarchical Token-Semantic

Audio Transformer), on the other hand, is a transformer-based model that uses four groups of Swin Transformer blocks [9] to capture complex patterns in audio spectrograms with a focus on optimization.

These encoders were used in Microsoft CLAP and LAION-AI CLAP, respectively (PANN in the former and HTSAT in the latter). Among the two, HTSAT is generally considered the more suitable option, particularly due to its strong performance on a variety of audio understanding tasks.

That said, MAEST [10] (Music Audio Efficient Spectrogram Transformer) is a newer encoder specifically designed for music-related tasks. Compared to HTSAT, it is a larger and more complex model, and it has shown promising results. This makes it a valuable candidate to evaluate in a contrastive learning setup focused on music, particularly in low-data scenarios where model efficiency and generalization are critical.

2.4 Model training

Training a contrastive learning model involves minimizing a loss function that brings matching audio-text pairs closer together in the embedding space, while pushing apart non-matching pairs. To achieve this, both audio and text inputs are passed through their respective encoders and then projected into a shared embedding space using modality-specific linear projections.

Although training all components jointly is standard practice, this approach can be computationally expensive. To address this, several alternatives have been proposed [11, 12], which aim to reduce training costs without significantly sacrificing performance.

One practical strategy in multimodal settings is to initialize the audio encoder with pretrained weights from a related domain, such as vision or general audio classification, rather than training from scratch. Another common approach is to freeze the text encoder, especially when it has already been pretrained on large-scale language corpora. These techniques help reduce computational demands while still enabling

effective contrastive learning.

2.5 Training datasets

Training contrastive learning models requires paired audio-text data, where the text can consist of tags or natural language descriptions. Typically, large-scale datasets are used to achieve strong performance in this setting.

For reference, the LAION-AI CLAP model for music was trained on the LAION-Audio-630k dataset (630,000 audios of human activities, natural sounds and audio effects), the AudioSet (approximately 2 million samples of human-labeled 10-second sound clips drawn from YouTube videos), and a combination of music-related datasets¹.

However, these datasets are either not specifically curated for music or contain noisy and low-quality annotations. Additionally, working with such large-scale datasets is not always practical due to computational limitations, especially in smaller-scale or academic environments.

¹Check reference for more details on the music datasets: https://github.com/LAION-AI/audio-dataset/blob/main/data_collection/README.md

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Training setup

Establishing a solid training setup involves carefully selecting both the data and the model architecture. As discussed in earlier sections, this project prioritizes high-quality, openly available audio-text datasets. For this purpose, the MTG-Jamendo dataset [13] is a strong fit.

3.1.1 Dataset

For training, the MTG-Jamendo split-0 is used, which is a standard partition for research. This split consists of 32,859 audio-text pairs for training and 11,101 for validation. The dataset is converted into the WebDataset format, a structure optimized for scalable machine learning workflows. In this format, each pair is represented by an audio path and a comma-separated list of tags associated with the track.

3.1.2 Model architecture

The models follow the LAION-AI CLAP architecture, which serves as the baseline for this project. This includes both the component structure and the training configuration. The architecture consists of separate encoders for audio and text, followed by linear projections into a shared embedding space.

To reduce training complexity, the text encoder is frozen during training, since it is already pretrained on large-scale language data. For the audio encoder, pretrained weights are used to avoid training from scratch.

By default, the HTSAT is used as the audio encoder. However, the MAEST encoder is also integrated into the implementation to enable comparison. This makes it possible to train models using either encoder within the same framework.

3.2 Evaluation setup

Choosing a meaningful evaluation strategy is essential for accurately assessing and comparing model performance. To this end, three distinct evaluation tasks are defined, each highlighting different aspects of multimodal learning: zero-shot classification using the GTZAN dataset [14], multi-label classification using the MagnaTagATune dataset [15], and text-to-music retrieval using the Song Describer dataset [16].

3.2.1 Zero-shot classification on the GTZAN dataset

Zero-shot classification tests a model’s ability to assign audio samples to predefined categories without task-specific training. Instead, the model matches audio to text representations of each category by comparing embeddings in a shared space.

The GTZAN dataset is well-suited for zero-shot classification, as it provides 30-second audio samples for 10 distinct music genres: blues, classical, country, disco, hip-hop, jazz, metal, pop, reggae, and rock. Each genre includes 100 samples, except for jazz, which has 99 due to a corrupted file.

To perform zero-shot classification, a text embedding is created for each genre using a simple prompt format: “This is a {genre} song.” These serve as the class representations in the embedding space. Next, audio embeddings are computed for all tracks. For each audio embedding, similarity scores are calculated with each of the text embeddings using the dot product. The genre corresponding to the highest similarity score is selected as the predicted label.

Finally, predicted labels are compared to ground truth annotations, and the overall classification accuracy is then used to evaluate model performance on this zero-shot task.

3.2.2 Multi-label classification on the MagnaTagATune dataset

Multi-label classification evaluates a model’s ability to assign multiple relevant tags to a single audio track. The MagnaTagATune dataset is well-suited for this task, containing 29-second clips annotated with one or more labels drawn from a pool of 188 music-related tags.

To simplify the task and ensure reliable evaluation, only the 50 most frequent tags are considered, following a common practice. The dataset is divided into training (15,244 samples), validation (1,529 samples), and test (4,332 samples) subsets. Audio embeddings are precomputed for all tracks.

A lightweight classifier is trained on top of these embeddings using a transfer learning approach. The classifier is a two-layer feedforward neural network (MLP) that takes an audio embedding as input and outputs probabilities for each of the 50 tags. A sigmoid activation function allows each tag to be predicted independently. Tags are assigned when their predicted probability exceeds a defined threshold, enabling multi-label predictions per track.

Evaluation is conducted using the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC), which measures the model’s capacity to distinguish between classes across various decision thresholds, and the Mean Average Precision (MAP), which evaluates the ranking quality and precision across all relevant labels, providing a robust framework for assessing how well the multimodal model captures diverse musical attributes in a multi-label context.

3.2.3 Text-to-music retrieval on the Song Describer dataset

Text-to-music retrieval evaluates the model’s ability to retrieve relevant audio tracks based on natural language queries. The Song Describer dataset is well-suited for this

task, as it contains audio tracks paired with human-written captions that describe musical content. For evaluation, the validated subset of the dataset is used, which includes 746 unique audio tracks.

However, the dataset contains a total of 1,106 audio-text pairs, since some tracks are associated with multiple captions. This adds value from an evaluation perspective, as it allows the model to retrieve a correct audio track based on a caption that may not be its exact pair.

To carry out the retrieval, embeddings are computed for all audio tracks and text captions. A similarity matrix is then built using the dot product between each text and audio embedding. Each caption is treated as a query, and all tracks are ranked based on similarity scores.

Performance is evaluated using Median Rank (MedR), which measures the median position of the correct audio track across all queries, and Recall at K (R@k), which indicates the proportion of queries for which the correct track appears in the top k results. These metrics together provide a strong indication of how effectively the model aligns text descriptions with musical content.

3.3 Experiments

This section outlines the experiments conducted throughout the project.

3.3.1 HTSAT-base (initialized weights) + RoBERTa (frozen)

A CLAP model is trained using the HTSAT audio encoder with initialized pre-trained weights², alongside a frozen RoBERTa text encoder. The specific HTSAT implementation used is the base version, designed to process 10-second audio clips. This model serves as the baseline for the project. Training a model with the same encoders as LAION-AI CLAP, but on a smaller dataset, ensures a fair comparison with other experimental models.

²Pretrained weights are available at the following link: <https://github.com/LAION-AI/CLAP/blob/main/README.md#reproducibility>

3.3.2 MAEST-10s (initialized weights) + RoBERTa (frozen)

An experimental CLAP model is trained using the MAEST audio encoder, specifically the “discogs-maest-10s-pw-129e” variant, which also processes 10-second audio segments. As with the baseline, the RoBERTa text encoder remains frozen, and pretrained weights initialize the audio encoder. The goal of this experiment is to compare the performance of the MAEST encoder against the baseline HTSAT within a multimodal representation setting.

3.3.3 Hyperparameters exploration

To better understand the impact of training configurations, various hyperparameter settings are explored throughout the training process.

A key parameter under investigation is batch size, which is known to be directly related to model performance in contrastive learning settings. However, due to computational constraints, the batch sizes used in this project are smaller than those commonly used in large-scale contrastive learning setups.

Furthermore, several hyperparameters intended to enhance generalization in low-data contexts are examined. In particular, weight decay and learning rate decay are explored as strategies to reduce overfitting and promote more stable training under low-data conditions.

3.3.4 Evaluation methods

For evaluation, two approaches are considered for computing audio embeddings: one involves extracting embeddings from a randomly selected 10-second segment of each audio track, and the other computes embeddings for every 10-second segment and averages them to obtain the final representation. These methods help assess how the choice of segment affects the quality of audio representations.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 HTSAT vs MAEST

The first comparison between models using different audio encoders has been conducted, with both models trained using a batch size of 64 and the default hyperparameters provided by the LAION-AI CLAP implementation. The results of this evaluation are shown in Table 1.

Task	Metric	HTSAT	MAEST
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	51.05	28.73
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.807	0.786
	MAP	0.284	0.263
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	140	198
	R@1	0.94	0.80
	R@5	4.42	2.95
	R@10	9.92	5.36

Table 1: Comparison of performance for models trained using HTSAT and MAEST audio encoders with batch size = 64, both initialized with pretrained weights.

The model using the HTSAT audio encoder demonstrates solid performance across the various tasks, particularly given the limited amount of training data used compared to the large-scale datasets employed in the original LAION-AI models. In

contrast, the model using the MAEST audio encoder shows significantly lower performance in most evaluation tasks.

Notably, the MAEST-based model appears to suffer from overfitting, suggested by the validation loss increasing significantly while the training loss decreases, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. To further explore this issue, the following section analyzes the impact of various hyperparameters, including those that may help improve generalization, such as weight decay and learning rate decay.

4.2 Hyperparameters effect

This section explores the effects of three key hyperparameters: batch size, weight decay, and learning rate decay. Batch size is evaluated using the HTSAT baseline model to understand its impact on performance in contrastive learning tasks. In contrast, weight decay, which helps prevent overfitting by discouraging large weights, and learning rate decay, which reduces the learning rate across layers to enable more stable convergence, are explored as strategies to address the overfitting observed in the MAEST-based model.

4.2.1 Batch size

The performance of the LAION-AI CLAP implementation, using the HTSAT-base audio encoder (initialized with pretrained weights) and the RoBERTa text encoder, has been evaluated with three different batch sizes: 16, 32, and 64. The results of this comparison are shown in Table 2.

As shown in Table 2, the relationship between batch size and performance is inconsistent across tasks when using pretrained weights. While larger batch sizes show improvements in multi-label classification, performance in zero-shot classification and text-to-music retrieval is less consistent. This behaviour may result from the pretrained weights already providing structured semantic representations. As a result, the model becomes less sensitive to the number of negative samples per batch, and thus to batch size.

Task	Metric	Batch 16	Batch 32	Batch 64
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	51.45	46.05	51.05
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.729	0.771	0.807
	MAP	0.215	0.244	0.284
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	129	135	140
	R@1	1.07	0.67	0.94
	R@5	4.42	5.50	4.42
	R@10	8.18	9.92	9.92

Table 2: Comparison of batch size performance for trained HTSAT models initialized with pretrained weights.

To further explore the role of batch size, the same experiment was conducted using randomly initialized weights for the HTSAT audio encoder. The results, presented in Table 3, demonstrate a clear and consistent trend: larger batch sizes lead to better performance across all tasks and metrics.

Task	Metric	Batch 16	Batch 32	Batch 64
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	28.43	32.33	36.54
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.727	0.763	0.788
	MAP	0.197	0.220	0.244
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	163	157	129
	R@1	0.67	1.07	1.34
	R@5	2.41	3.62	4.02
	R@10	5.63	7.51	8.04

Table 3: Comparison of batch size performance for trained HTSAT models initialized with random weights.

Overall, while larger batch sizes typically improve performance in contrastive learning by increasing the diversity of negative samples, this effect is more pronounced when training from scratch. With pretrained weights, the encoder already captures semantically meaningful representations, which may reduce its sensitivity to batch size within the limited range evaluated here. Additionally, fine-tuning a pretrained encoder can introduce greater variability across runs, since optimization relies on

smaller adjustments to established features. This increased sensitivity likely explains the less consistent trends observed in Table 2, in contrast to the more predictable improvements seen when training from scratch.

4.2.2 Weight Decay

Weight decay has been evaluated as a potential method to mitigate overfitting when training the CLAP model with the MAEST audio encoder. Table 4 compares the performance across different weight decay values, with $wd = 0$ serving as the baseline.

Task	Metric	wd=0	wd=1e-4	wd=1e-2
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	28.73	30.13	27.63
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.786	0.781	0.797
	MAP	0.263	0.249	0.274
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	198	239	211
	R@1	0.80	0.67	0.54
	R@5	2.95	3.62	3.62
	R@10	5.36	5.90	6.30

Table 4: Comparison of weight decay effect for trained MAEST models initialized with pretrained weights.

The results in Table 4 show no consistent performance improvement with the use of weight decay. Differences between configurations are small and vary across tasks, suggesting that changes cannot be conclusively attributed to weight decay. This is further supported by Figure 2, which shows an overall increase in validation loss.

These observations indicate that weight decay has a limited effect in this setting, potentially because other regularization strategies, such as random sampling and data augmentation, are already applied during training.

4.2.3 Learning Rate Decay

Learning rate decay has been applied to the MAEST encoder layers to progressively reduce the learning rate of the lower layers, aiming to mitigate overfitting. Results are presented in Table 5, comparing two different decay factors against the baseline setting $\text{lrd} = 1.0$.

Task	Metric	$\text{lrd}=1.0$	$\text{lrd}=0.9$	$\text{lrd}=0.8$
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	28.73	29.03	30.03
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.786	0.781	0.786
	MAP	0.263	0.261	0.259
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	198	247	226
	R@1	0.80	0.80	0.67
	R@5	2.95	3.08	3.75
	R@10	5.36	6.03	6.57

Table 5: Comparison of learning rate decay effect for trained MAEST models initialized with pretrained weights.

As with weight decay, the results in Table 5 show no consistent improvements relative to the baseline. The observed differences are small and vary across tasks, while the validation loss in Figure 2 increases during training, further indicating that overfitting is not mitigated.

This outcome may be due to the MAEST encoder being initialized with pretrained weights, meaning its lower layers already provide well-structured and transferable audio representations. Consequently, further lowering their learning rate has limited effect, as these layers require minimal adjustment during fine-tuning

4.3 Evaluation methods

The two different methods for computing audio embeddings, using a single random 10-second segment versus averaging embeddings across all 10-second segments, have been evaluated using the LAION-AI CLAP model (checkpoint “music_audioset_epoch_

15_esc_90.14.pt”). Results are shown in Table 6.

The choice of a pretrained LAION-AI model, rather than one trained in this work, does not affect the validity of the comparison, as the focus here is on evaluation methodology rather than model performance. Additionally, including a model trained on a large-scale dataset provides a useful reference for assessing the gap between the limited-data approaches in this project and large-data baselines.

Task	Metric	Random segment	Averaging
Zero-shot classification (GTZAN)	Accuracy	71.27	72.37
Multi-label classification (MTT)	AUROC	0.876	0.887
	MAP	0.391	0.409
Text-to-music retrieval (SD)	MedR ↓	24	20
	R@1	6.97	6.70
	R@5	23.32	25.60
	R@10	37.00	39.01

Table 6: Comparison of evaluation methods for the LAION-AI CLAP pretrained checkpoint.

As shown in Table 6, averaging across segments leads to better performance in nearly all cases. This result is expected, as the averaging method captures a more comprehensive representation of each audio track, making it a more robust and reliable approach. However, this method is more computationally demanding, particularly for long recordings, and should be applied with consideration of resource constraints. For the datasets used in this work, audio tracks were short enough to make averaging feasible, and thus this method was adopted for all reported results.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Discussion

The experiments presented offer a comprehensive comparison of the HTSAT and MAEST audio encoders, various hyperparameter settings, and evaluation methodologies for CLAP models under limited data and computational resources. Several key insights emerge from the results.

First, HTSAT consistently outperforms MAEST across all tasks, despite both being initialized with pretrained weights and trained under identical conditions. This suggests HTSAT is better suited to scenarios with limited training data. In contrast, MAEST showed signs of overfitting, as evidenced by the divergence between training and validation losses, indicating weaker generalization capabilities.

The hyperparameter analysis offers further insight into model behaviour under different conditions. Larger batch sizes improve performance when training from scratch, likely due to increased diversity of negative samples in contrastive learning. However, this effect is reduced and inconsistent when pretrained weights are used, implying that pretrained encoders already encode rich semantic information that diminishes sensitivity to batch size.

Weight decay and learning rate decay, explored as potential remedies for MAEST's

overfitting, demonstrated limited effectiveness. Neither method consistently improved performance relative to the baseline, and validation losses generally increased. This may be explained by existing regularization methods such as random sampling and data augmentation, along with well-structured representations in pretrained lower layers that limit the impact of additional constraints or learning rate modifications.

Finally, the evaluation methodology comparison confirms that averaging embeddings over all 10-second audio segments leads to more reliable and generally improved performance compared to using a single random segment. Although computationally more demanding, this approach was practical for the datasets used here and was adopted as the standard evaluation method.

5.2 Conclusions

Several important conclusions can be drawn from this work.

First, the LAION-AI CLAP implementation serves as an effective baseline for learning multimodal representations, delivering solid performance across a range of tasks while providing a flexible and modular framework. The open-source implementation developed here includes a robust evaluation methodology for music-focused audio-text representations, designed to be well-structured, reusable, and easily extensible for future research.

Regarding audio encoders, HTSAT outperforms MAEST in the low-data regime considered in this work. Although MAEST has a larger and more complex architecture, common regularization techniques such as weight decay and learning rate decay did not lead to notable improvements in its performance. Therefore, smaller encoders like HTSAT appear better suited to scenarios with limited data and resources.

However, model size alone may not fully account for the observed performance gap. Architectural differences and variations in pretraining between HTSAT and MAEST likely play a substantial role in these results. Regardless of the underlying cause, in the context of this project, the combination of HTSAT initialized with

pretrained weights and a frozen RoBERTa text encoder proved to be the most effective configuration for the LAION-AI CLAP framework under limited resources.

Another key insight is the critical role of data volume, not only for learning robust multimodal representations but also for achieving reliable and meaningful evaluation. Models trained with limited data remain substantially behind state-of-the-art performance, highlighting the dependence of contrastive learning methods on large datasets.

Finally, under constrained resources that restrict batch size, performance appears more influenced by factors such as audio encoder weight initialization. The inability to train with larger batch sizes is a significant limitation of this study.

5.3 Future work

A natural next step for this project is to investigate a simplified version of the MAEST-based model, for example, by removing certain layers or reducing its dimensionality, to improve its suitability for low-data settings.

Another potential direction for future work involves training models under low-data conditions but with larger batch sizes, which requires more computational resources. Additionally, expanding the amount of training data would enable a more comprehensive analysis of how both batch size and data volume influence model performance.

Finally, a more exploratory path could involve experimenting with alternative encoder combinations, including newer audio and text encoders, or investigating different approaches to learning multimodal audio-text representations beyond the conventional contrastive learning framework, such as approaches benefiting from large language models (LLMs) [17].

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Appendix A

Training and Validation Loss Graphs

(a) audio encoders comparison

(b) batch size comparison

(c) weight decay comparison

(d) learning rate decay comparison

Figure 1: Training loss curves: (a) audio encoders comparison, (b) batch size comparison, (c) weight decay comparison, (d) learning rate decay comparison.

(a) audio encoders comparison

(b) batch size comparison

(c) weight decay comparison

(d) learning rate decay comparison

Figure 2: Validation loss curves: (a) audio encoders comparison, (b) batch size comparison, (c) weight decay comparison, (d) learning rate decay comparison.